

At the beach on the Island of Sylt. Walter Altenkirchen

PARTNERSHIP INVENTORY WP 4.1

Taking Stock: An Inventory of existing Partnership Programmes at North Sea region World Heritage Sites and Protected Areas

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Preface

This inventory is a deliverable for the PROWAD LINK Work Package 4: Brand engagement by partnership programmes. It provides background information and analysis. The overview will be used to develop a transnational North Sea Region partnership scheme based on the concept “Nature-Business-Benefit-Cycle (NBBC)”. A transnational scheme will build on, extend and sustain existing collaborations and networks.

The aim of PROWAD LINK scheme is to connect the regional networks in a transnational context by building long-term partnerships with cross-sectorial supporters and link these to the World Heritage brand.

The information in this inventory was collected through the cooperation of PROWAD LINK project partners. We extend our gratitude for the information and cooperation.

Overview of the Inventory

1. Introduction

One of the objectives of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) is to encourage the identification, protection and preservation of cultural and natural heritage around the world considered to be of outstanding value to humanity. This is described in an international treaty known as the 1972 Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage. The North Sea Region is endowed with nature and culture assets that are designated by UNESCO as World Heritage Sites or by other agreements as protected areas. These assets need to be conserved, and are at the same time valued for economic activities such as tourism.

The requirements for conservation and business need to be balanced so as to yield benefits for the environment, society and economy. This calls for innovation of management systems to involve multiple stakeholders and multiple goals. Nature management involves the establishment of policies, continuous monitoring of their proper implementation, by members of a governing body or organization. It includes the mechanisms needed to balance stakeholder interests and accountability (Arnouts et al., 2012). In the case of the North Sea Region, increased pressures on the environment by pollution and rise in sea levels add complexity to the management of the nature and heritage areas. By adapting Ostrom's 2009 General Framework for Analysing Sustainability of Socio-Ecological Systems, a depiction of the factors that interact in management of protected nature areas is given in figure 1.

There are different governance approaches taken on local and regional level at the North Sea Region. These are to safe guard the interests of varied stakeholders and achieve the, sometimes-competing goals, of conservation and attractive business setting.

Figure 1: Framework of factors that interact in management of nature in the North Sea Region. (Adapted from Ostrom, 2009).

The nature assets such as biodiversity, unique landscapes, and culture assets such as a rich history due to over 400 years of human settlement, available in the North Sea Region, require constant monitoring to maintain their quality. The benefits to the community living in or near the areas need to be safe-guarded. These ambitions need sustainable strategies to promote benefit sharing between nature and the human population.

In order to improve relations between stakeholders and promote sustainable tourism, partnership and collaboration strategies have been implemented. A framework that illustrates the development of such partnerships is given in figure 2.

An Evolutionary Model of Tourism Partnerships

Figure 2: Tourism partnership model. Source: (Graci, 2012 as in Selin and Chavez 1995: 848).

For the purposes of this inventory, we adopt Laing et al.'s (2008, p. 4) definition of a sustainable tourism partnerships/collaborations, which was developed based on Bramwell and Lane (2000):

“ [Partnerships/Collaborations are] regular, cross-sectoral interactions over an extended period of time between parties, based on at least some agreed rules or norms, intended to address a common issue or to achieve a specific policy goal or goals, which cannot be solved by the partners individually and involving pooling and sharing of appreciations or resources, mutual influence, accountability, commitment, participation, trust and respect and transparency.”

Scope of the Inventory

The inventory will look at management institutions in the Wadden Sea, Wash/ North Norfolk and West Norwegian Fjords with a focus on Geirangerfjord. In following sections, a brief description of the three areas is given.

1. The Wadden Sea World Heritage Site

The Wadden Sea is the largest unbroken system of intertidal sand and mud flats in the world. It includes the Dutch Wadden Sea Conservation Area, the German Wadden Sea National Parks of Lower Saxony and Schleswig-Holstein, and most of the Danish Wadden Sea maritime conservation area. It is listed by UNESCO as a World Heritage Site because it is one of the few remaining intertidal ecosystems where natural processes continue to function largely undisturbed (Waddensea-worldheritage.org website).

2. The Wash

The Wash is an outstanding shallow bay about 20kms wide and 30kms long. It borders West Norfolk and opens into the North Sea. It is the largest estuary system in the United Kingdom. There are varied habitats in the area such as saltmarshes, saline lagoons, shingle banks, sand dunes and mudflats. It is the second largest mudflat in Britain (West Norfolk website). It is designated as a Special Area of Conservation (SAC) under the European Union Habitats Directive.

3. West Norwegian Fjords - Geirangerfjord and Nærøyfjord World Heritage Site

The West Norwegian Fjords - Geirangerfjord and Nærøyfjord is situated in south-western Norway, north-east of Bergen. Geirangerfjord and Nærøyfjord are 120 km from one another. The two fjords are among the world's longest and deepest. They are considered archetypical fjord landscapes. They are characterised by exceptional natural beauty due to their narrow and steep-sided crystalline rock walls 1400m high from the Norwegian Sea and extending 500m below sea level. The numerous waterfalls and free-flowing rivers, deciduous and coniferous woodlands and forests, glacial lakes, glaciers, rugged mountains and a range of other natural attributes combine towards making Geirangerfjord and Nærøyfjord among the most scenically outstanding landscapes in the world. These and other features merited their designation as a World Heritage Site (whc.unesco.org website)

Purpose of the Inventory

The aim of this report is to provide an overview of existing partner programmes (in the three regions) that are concerned with promoting sustainable tourism practices in protected nature areas. The focus will be on how the partnership programmes are organized. The programmes are in some instances initiated by protected area management to promote local commitment for conservation, and concessions from business to act in a sustainable way. This inventory presents the benefits of these programmes for nature, the community and sustainable business. The partnerships/collaborations are expected to enhance the exploitation of nature and culture assets of the protected areas, while adhering to the three sustainability principles of people, planet and profit.

The Approach: methods used to compile the inventory

The report used data collected through a desk study (analysis of reports, documents and existing literature on the areas). Additional data from observations and participation in regional meetings in the Wadden Sea area was collected. Inquiries of how existing programmes work were also done via phone calls and email. This yielded more information.

Formation of Young Dune
landscape on Rottumerplaat
island in the Wadden sea,
Netherlands

Photo by: Rudmer Zwerver

Institutional Landscapes of

Selected regions

Wadden Sea World Heritage Site: the Netherlands

There was no umbrella organization managing the entire Wadden Sea World Heritage area situated in the Netherlands. The administration was partly done by the national government through the Rijkswaterstaat and Ministry of Economic Affairs who managed the Wadden Sea. The Dutch provinces of Noord-Holland, Friesland and Groningen and their waterboards also partly managed the area. In addition, the municipalities of the five islands that border the protected area, and the twelve municipalities on the mainland also managed the Wadden Sea area in the Netherlands to varied extents. This was the situation up until 2015.

The management of the Wadden Sea World Heritage in the Netherlands was highly stratified. Following a report to the government, a new structure was agreed on in October 2017. In this new structure, a managing authority will be formulated for Dutch Wadden Sea World Heritage area. The ministries of LNV and Infrastructure and Water (IenW) formulated the framework and tasks of the authority informed by an independent survey. The new structure consists of: the Wadden Sea Administrative Consultation, the Environment Council and the Wadden Sea Management Authority. The Administrative Consultation Wadden is led by the Minister for IenW and members include LNV, the Wadden provinces, coastal and island municipalities, water boards and the chairman of the Wadden Environmental Council. It focuses on strategic decisions over Wadden policy. The Wadden Environmental Council is headed by a King's Commissioner. It focuses on stakeholder interests. The Ministry of LNV has also set up a Client Consultation Authority for the Wadden Sea Management Authority. This new institutional structure is work in progress and more development is expected in the near future.

The protected nature areas are managed by conservation organization including the State Forestry Commission, Natuurmonumenten and Fryske Gea. There are three national parks in the area, namely Duinen van Texel, Schiermonnikoog and Lauwersmeer. These parks are administered by nature management and conservation organizations. It is important to note that the parks are small in area compared to the Wadden Sea World Heritage area.

Wadden Sea World Heritage Site: Germany

The German Wadden Sea areas in the three regions of Schleswig-Holstein, Hamburg and Niedersachsen are administered as national parks and designated as UNESCO biosphere reserves.

In Schleswig-Holstein, the Ministry of Environment delegates the management of the protected area to the National Park Administration. The decisions about the park are discussed by the National Park Committees of Nordfriesland and Dithmarschen. The park administration is supported by nature conservation associations in the area. The associations provide wardens for the National Park areas, run information centres, support environmental monitoring and conduct many guided nature tours in the National Park.

In Hamburg, the National Park administration is part of the Hamburg Authority for the Environment and Energy in Hamburg. The headquarters for fieldwork is in Neuwerk. The National Park administration develops concepts for protection of the park and monitor its compliance. Its employees cooperate with the residents and volunteer associations such as the Jordsand association for the protection of seabirds and nature.

In Niedersachsen (Lower Saxony), the Wadden Sea has been protected as a national park since 1986. The National Park Act of 2010 expanded its area to approximately 345,000 hectares making it the second largest German national park. It is administered by the National Park Administration in Wilhelmshaven, under guidance by the Lower Saxony Ministry of Environment and Climate Protection, and in close collaboration with other state agencies, local authorities and organizations. An advisory board representing all relevant stakeholder groups gives advice on management issues. Several green NGOs and municipalities are involved as carrying organisations for visitor centres and other education and interpretation activities. Nature associations monitor and supervise certain parts of the National Park on behalf of the national park administration. Since 2015, fulltime rangers serve as custodians of the national park area on site, providing information to tourists and inhabitants. Monitoring, custodial (warden duties) and on-site management is supported by volunteers.

Wadden Sea World Heritage Site: Denmark

The Danish Ministry of Environment -Nature Agency or "Naturstyrelsen" is responsible for nature restoration, national parks, leisure activities and forestry. The Danish Wadden Sea area is administered as a National Park. The Wadden Sea National Park is established as an independent state foundation under the Ministry of Environment. The Park has a National Park Board with 15 members from the Ministry of Environment, municipalities, advisory councils, NGOs and relevant interest groups. The Board has an Advisory Council with thirty members. The members consist of representatives appointed from relevant organizations or specific local communities. The Danish national park covers the conservation area, as well as whole islands and parts of the mainland.

Wash and North Norfolk Coast, England

The Wash is the largest marine embayment in Britain and the second largest expanse of mud and sandflats. It is home to the largest colony of common seals in Britain. The North Norfolk coast is the best British example of a barrier beach system. It was among the ten most important wetland sites in Britain for numbers of waterfowl. The area is important for its marine communities and rich in flora and fauna.

The Wash and North Norfolk coast is managed collaboratively by varied authorities. They are led by Eastern Inshore Fisheries and Conservation Authority (EIFCA) and includes Norfolk County Council, North Norfolk District Council, Boston Borough Council, Lincolnshire County Council, East Lindsey District Council, Natural England (Norfolk & East Midlands Teams), Environment Agency (Anglian Region), Fenland District Council, Internal Drainage Boards, King's Lynn Conservancy Board, King's Lynn and West Norfolk Borough Council, and Wells Harbour Commissioners.

The area has a management scheme aimed to ensure conservation of the Area of Outstanding Natural Beauty (AONB) through the Norfolk Coast Partnership and the Wash European Marine Site through the Wash and North Norfolk Marine Partnership (WNNMP). The landowners' associations are also involved in protected area stewardship.

World Heritage Site Geiranger Fjord

The West Norwegian Fjords is managed by the World Heritage Council founded in 2006. The council's objective was to explore the opportunities that come with the inscription of the area into the UNESCO's World Heritage List. The council promotes collaboration between the regional world heritage foundations and information exchange between local. Regional and national participants in the two areas that fall under the West Norwegian Fjords. The council's purpose is *'to ensure that the world heritage statues is looked after in line with the intentions of the World Heritage Convention, the guidelines of the Convention and the administrative plan for the world heritage area'* ([Nærøyfjorden World Heritage Park Council website](#)). The area is regulated by national acts covering buildings near the sea, open-air recreation, forest protection, traffic on uncultivated land and waters, farm land, wildlife, pollution, salmonid and freshwater fish and protection of watercourses from development (World Heritage datasheet).

At the Nærøyfjord site, there is a World Heritage Park. The World Heritage Park was created as a foundation in 2008 by Sogn of Fjordane County and the municipalities of Aurland, Lærdal, Vik and Voss. The organisation is led by a board. There is a team that handles day to day administration and field support. This team works on concrete projects and measures within the park's primary areas of commitment such as; nature and culture-based industry, distribution of information for the area, develop local hosting skills and education, administration of the cultural heritage and landscape, facilitate travel and strengthening a local common identity and brand.

At the Geirangerfjord site, the protected area is managed by the governors of Møre and Romsdal counties. The Storfjord Project report describes a management strategy to maintain active farming and spread awareness locally of cultural values of the landscape. In both sites, the Directorates for Nature Management and the Norwegian Nature Inspectorate, the Directorate for Cultural Heritage, the Regional Divisions for Environmental Conservation and Agriculture and Departments of Cultural Affairs and Planning are government agencies that cooperate with them (World Heritage datasheet).

Summary

The institutional landscape in the five countries, hosting the protected nature areas, are different. The Danish and Germany areas have centralised structures while the Netherlands, England and Norway are decentralised. This influences the design and make-up of the partnership/collaboration programmes in the respective countries.

Wadden sea mud-flats of a tidal marsh where new land is being created on the Groningen coast in the Netherlands

Photo by: Rudmer Zwerver

Description of existing Partnership Programmes

The sites (described in section 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3) are managed to conserve nature, preserve culture and promote sustainable tourism. There are partnership (collaboration) programmes at the sites that work with local businesses to enhance nature protection and sustainable economic development. Partnership programmes are an organisational form that involves “*the voluntary pooling of resources (labour, money, information, etc) between two or more parties to accomplish collaborative goals (sustainable tourism, conservation)*” Selin & Chavez, (1995) p.2 (845).

In the tables that follow, the programmes at protected areas are described loosely based on the partnership framework developed by Kanya et al., 2016 for partnerships in the health sector. The tables summarise the partnership structure, partner performance, partnership activities and partnership’s added value.

1. Programmes in The Netherlands

Previously, the Netherlands had a highly stratified nature management system. This led to numerous partnership programmes with varied goals. The programmes in the Netherlands have been categorised using the objectives of the organizations leading the programmes.

Table 1: Overview of partnership programmes in the Netherlands oriented towards quality standards

QUALITY STANDARD	
Organization name	Waddengoud
Type	Certification as regional product
Focus	Production of Sustainable regional products
Criteria	Different criteria per product. Strong focus on local producers and gastronomy. The products come from the Wadden sea region. Criteria built on other known and accepted certifications.
Membership/Partners	SMEs and organisations
Number of partners	-
Funding	Partners pay for the quality mark
Benefits to partners	Use of official logo/certificate. The Waddengoud logo but also World Heritage logo Access to Waddenmarktplaats: a collection off web shops and
Activities for partners	Participation in local product promotional activities
Benefits to nature	Sustainable production of products and services
Monitoring and evaluation	Monitor that standards are adhered to, and for renewal of certification.

Table 2: Overview of partnership programmes in the Netherlands oriented towards marketing.

MARKETING				
Organization name	Stitching Regiomarketing NoordOostFryslan (NOF)	Holland boven Amsterdam	Noardwest	Waddenland
Type	Regional Marketing Cooperation	Destination marketing organisation	Regional Marketing Cooperation	Regional Cooperation
Focus	Tourism	Tourism	Tourism	Tourism Marketing and Promotions
Criteria	No criteria other than working in tourism or related business.	No criteria other than working in Restaurant & Tours, or related business	No criteria other than working in Restaurant & Tours, or related business	No criteria other than working in Restaurant & Tours or related branch
Membership/ Partners	SME's	SME's	SME's	SME's
Number of	Approx. 400	-	-	90
Funding	The Market: From participation fees for SME trainings and advertisement Relevant Municipalities double money that comes from the market using a <i>click on</i> model.	From associated regions	From associated regions	
Benefits to partners	Communication tools Networking opportunities for SMEs Offer workshops	Market communication tools Networking Offer workshops	Market communication tools, Business to business networks Offer workshops	Communication tools Networking Offer on workshops
Activities for partners	Learning network, exchange meetings, marketing	Network meetings Participation in promotional events	Learning network, exchange meetings, marketing	Learning network Exchange meetings Marketing, Access to communication material
Benefits to nature	-	-	-	Promotion of value of nature and culture
Monitoring and evaluation	Development of the annual plan	Annual meeting to tell entrepreneurs of opportunities	Annual meetings to tell entrepreneurs of opportunities	-

Table 3: Overview of a form of partnership programmes in the Netherlands oriented towards National Parks

	NATIONAL PARKS		
Organization name	National Park Lauwersmeer	National Park Schiermonnikoog	National Park Duinen Van Texel
Type	Nature conservation	Nature conservation	Nature conservation and sustainable tourism
Focus	Balance the economic and nature aspects of Lauwersmeer.	National Park management	Promotion of conservation values by hospitality entrepreneurs in the national park area
Criteria	No criteria other than having interest in management and benefit of nature	None	Promote nature, culture and landscape value of Texel
Membership/ Partners	Work with marketing organizations, SMEs, volunteer's forestry authorities and other relevant partners in the region	Site managers, governments and interest groups including - Entrepreneurs Association among other partners	Texel Entrepreneurs Platform (TOP) among other partners
Number of partners	-	-	130 ambassadors (from TOP)
Funding	State Forest Authority (Staatsbosbeheer) Other relevant local authorities	Relevant authorities	State Forestry Authority (Staatsbosbeheer)
Benefits to partners	Nature conservation and promotion Raise awareness on value of natural environment	Nature-oriented recreation and quality improvement of facilities Communication and education Facilitating and stimulating (scientific) research	Promotional plans from the recreation working group. Communication and education materials
Activities for partners	Nature conservation and promotion	-	Promotion of the nature and culture area
Benefits to nature	Conservation activities Research on relevant areas	Nature management and development	Nature management and conservation
Monitoring and evaluation	Through the State Forest Authority (Staatsbosbeheer)	Monitoring of site by relevant authorities.	Monitoring site by relevant State Forest Authority

Table 4: Overview of partnership programmes in the Netherlands oriented towards Nature Organizations

	NATURE ORGANIZATIONS		
Organization name	Staatsbosbeheer	Natuurmonumenten	Fryske Gea
Type	Nature (forest) organisation	Individual membership	Regional cooperation
Focus	Nature protection	Nature protection	Nature protection
Criteria	Feeling one with nature Knowledge exchange, Attend meetings 4x a year	Interest in protection of nature.	Conservation of regional nature and culture value
Membership/Partners	SMEs, Farmers	Anyone including SMEs	
Number of partners	31 Best practice entrepreneurial cases on their website	-	> 35,000
Funding	National Government	Membership fee and donations	Membership Fee
Benefits to partners	Access to knowledge from experts in this department	Include reduced visit rates at other Natuurmonumenten managed sites	Lasting pleasure from the Frisian nature Discount on walking, sailing and cycling excursions for the whole family. Access to regional nature guide ' <i>Discover the Frisian nature</i> '
Activities for partners	Green energy Forest and natural habitat restoration Sustainable product development	-	Sailing and walking excursions Cultural activities
Benefits to nature	Conservation initiatives Nature management	Conservation of underwater nature through mapping and restoration	Nature conservation initiative for varied species and sites
Monitoring and evaluation	By scientists and experts affiliated to the authority	Depend on ongoing projects	Depend on ongoing initiatives

Table 5: Overview of partnership programmes in the Netherlands established as foundations.

FOUNDATIONS		
Organization name	Waddenvereniging	Wad500 (part of Waddenvereniging)
Type	Foundation	Business networks
Focus	Nature protection and conservation	Nature protection & tourism
Criteria	Anyone wishing to support nature protection	-
Membership/Partners	Anyone	SMEs operating in the Wadden sea area.
Number of partners	-	-
Funding	Membership fee and donations	Membership fee
Benefits to partners	A voice for conservation of nature value of the Wadden Sea Knowledge on conservation needs of the area	Networking opportunities Access to knowledge and capacity building WADDEN magazine four times a year Priority with sponsorship opportunities and advertising in the WADDEN magazine.
Activities for partners	Volunteer activities	Networking meetings
Benefits to nature	Conservation and protection of Wadden sea area from human activities (e.g. Gas extraction and military activities), through human activities (e.g. strengthen of the World Heritage brand value, management and policy, disaster relief).	Promotion of best business practice
Monitoring and	By scientists and experts affiliated to the foundation	-

2. Programmes in Germany

The National Park brand is well established in Germany. The partner programmes of the National Park Authorities are similarly structured due to close cooperation. The programmes are networks as well as label schemes and they are embedded in the nationwide partnership programme of the umbrella organisation Nationale Naturlandschaften e.V. (NNL National Natural Landscapes), which has defined minimum criteria for the partnership scheme itself and the label awarding. The aim is to foster regional sustainable development, to raise awareness and provide information to guests, to protect the environment and promote the protected nature sites.

Table 6: Overview of Partnership Programmes in the German Wadden Sea area.

NATIONAL PARKS			
	Nationalpark Niedersachsen (Lower Saxony)	Nationalpark Schleswig-Holstein	Nationalpark Hamburgisches Wattenmeer (Hamburg)
Type	Partner programme Nationalpark and Biosphere (Cobranding World Heritage)	Partner programme Nationalpark and Biosphere	Cooperation
Focus	National Park and biosphere reserve	National Park	National Park
Criteria	Criteria with focus on sustainability, regionality, environment-friendly business, social engagement, quality and respect for nature are to be met, also mandatory participation in trainings offered Commitment to the National Park goals and to cooperation	Criteria with focus on sustainability and respect for nature are to be met, also mandatory participation in trainings offered	Cooperation through declaration of working in a sustainable way SME: Criteria similar to Lower Saxony (cooperation agreement)
Membership/partners	SME's, municipalities, National park guides, schools, agriculture, educational institutions	SMEs, municipalities, nature conservation associations	Volunteer associations, financial institutions, SMEs
Number of partners	>270	>180	-
Funding	Public funding programme and members fees	Public funding programme and members fees	
Benefits to partners	A direct line to the National Park Administration exclusive information from the National Park network connections to other Partners with the option of joint action new advertising opportunities through a common Internet platform Use of logo and WH-Logo, communication material Access to National Park information material Promotion at own website and annual network meeting and trainings (cross sector). http://www.nationalpark-partner-wattenmeer-nds.de/	a direct line to the National Park Administration exclusive information from the National Park network connections to other Partners with the option of joint action new advertising opportunities through a common Internet platform display of brochures in the National Park Information Centres a detailed information package for the partners, their guests and staff www.nationalpark-partner-sh.de	Mentioning on NP website, logo use
Activities for partners	Trainings Network meetings Organization of promoting events (Biosphären-Markt, Biosphären-Menü-Tage, Zugvogeltage.)	Ambassador of the National Park idea Friendly and competent advisor in National Park matters Trainings Network meetings	Conducting nature tours and guides Conducting monitoring of the nature area
Benefits to nature	Promotion of environmentally friendly and sustainable tourism Quality supplier of nature related products and services Regional commitment and motivation; Increased awareness on the value of nature	Promotion of environmentally friendly and sustainable a quality supplier of nature related products and services Regional commitment and motivation.	Improve nature protection Increased awareness on the value of nature
Monitoring and evaluation	By relevant National Park Authority/ multistakeholder steering committee as approving body	Management by relevant National Park Authority / multi stakeholder steering committee as approving body	By relevant National Park Authority /cooperation with Lower Saxon steering committee for SME

Table 7: Summary of Quality Programme in the German Wadden Sea area.

	QUALITY STANDARD
Organization name	Wattenmeer-Produkte
Type	Certification as regional product
Focus	Production of Sustainable regional products
Criteria	Strong focus on local producers The products come from the Wadden sea region. Sustainable production
Membership/Partners	SMEs and organisations
Number of partners	>15
Funding	certification
Benefits to partners	Use of official logo/certificate. Promotion at own website www.wattenmeerprodukte.de network connections to other partners with the option of joint action and new distribution channels
Activities for partners	Participation in local product promotional activities Events: Biosphären-Markt, Biosphären-Menü-Tage
Benefits to nature	Sustainable production of products and services
Monitoring and evaluation	Management by relevant National Park Authority / multi stakeholder steering committee as approving body

3. Partnership programmes in Denmark

The Danish Wadden Sea is managed by a National park board, National park secretary and National park council - National Park Vadehavet. The National Park has a partnership programme which has several levels. The partners support the National Park idea and nature protection. They understand the mission statement and participate in trainings depending on their different roles/types.

Table 8: Overview of Danish Wadden Sea National Park partnership programme.

	National Park Vadehavet Partnership Programme types				
Programme Type	National Park partner	National Park ambassador	National Park products: Food and non-food	National Park training and research	World heritage Denmark Partner
Type	Support National Park Idea, support nature protection	National Park Partner	National Park Product Partner (Food or Non-food)	National Park Research or education partner	National Park World heritage partner
Focus	National Park	National Park	National Park	National Park	National Park
Criteria	Presentation of Nationalpark mission, participation course/e-learning course	Participation introduction course and follow-ups. Participation Partner meetings, hospitality Nationalpark. Distribute communication materials	Non-food and food: use of Logo Nationalpark. The products shall be evaluated and approved by the Partner Committee in accordance with the assessment form.	Relevant qualifications as an expert	Need to attend training courses
Membership/ partners	Anyone with interest	Organisations in the 4 Wadden sea municipalities which can create content for the national park. SME's, Museums, institutions	Producers of non-food products based on local raw materials, such as clothing or art. And producers of food such as restaurants	Relevant experts	Anyone with interest
Number of partners	-	-	-	-	-
Funding	-	-	-	-	-
Benefits to partners	Welcome package, communication material. Newsletter and participation of a closed Facebook group. Invitation for activities	Welcome package, Invitation for partner meetings and special meetings. Access to grants, Celebration National park day. Information about grants and participation of projects. Delivery of park material once a year.	Visibility on NP website. Access to protected name as well as logo and stickers with logo for National Park Wadden Sea and Denmark's National Parks.	Research opportunities	Welcome package Communication material Access to Newsletter
Activities for partners	Promote nature conservation	Promote nature conservation	Promote sustainable regional products	Conduct research about the nature and culture	Promote nature conservation and value
Benefits to nature	Promote nature conservation	Promote nature conservation	Promote nature protection through sustainable production	Promote nature education and science	Promote nature conservation and raise pride of local citizen
Monitoring and evaluation	By National Park	By National Park	By National Park	By National Park	By National Park

4. Programmes in the Wash and Norfolk, England

The Wash and Norfolk area has a number of partnerships with varied goals.

Table 9: Overview of partnership programmes in the Wash and North Norfolk area.

Organization name	Visit the Broads (Broads Tourism)	Norfolk Coast Partnership	Your Norfolk Coast	the Wash and North Norfolk Marine Partnership
Type	Partnership	Cooperation	Tool for SMEs	Collaboration
Focus	tourism	Nature management	Tourism & nature	Nature management
Criteria	Pledge to 'offer a high-quality experience for all customers which exceeds their expectations, provides excellent value for money and encourages them to return for more'. Support Responsible Tourism	The Norfolk Coast Partnership aims to conserve and enhance the natural beauty of the Norfolk Coast area of outstanding natural beauty, to facilitate and enhance the public enjoyment, understanding and appreciation of the area and to provide sustainable forms of social and economic development that in themselves conserve and enhance the area's natural beauty.	Be located in the West or North Norfolk area	Relevant concerned authorities
Membership/partners	Tourism and leisure SME's. Also, corporate partners	Local authorities	Interested businesses	Local communities and management groups working together to protect marine heritage
Number of partners	135+	Relevant local authorities There is a team of staff	-	3 Communities – Boston Advisory Group, King's Lynn Joint Advisory Group and North Norfolk Advisory Group. 20 Management groups 6 Conservation Groups
Funding	Membership subscription cost; From 90£ up to 300£ (depending on business turnover), Local & District councils 120£	Central and local government. (Including- Defra and Norfolk County Council, North Norfolk District Council, the Borough Council of Kings Lynn and West Norfolk and Great Yarmouth Borough Council) Also, charitable sources	The Rural Development Program for England (RDPE) Norfolk Coast & Broads Local Action Group Funded by Defra and the EU.	Depends on projects and project partners
Benefits to partners	Use of Visit the Broads Marketing and several communication channels. Facilitate business to business networks Access to photo gallery Access to information sources and improved purchasing terms from corporate trade partnership programme.	To bring about the sustainable management of the Norfolk Coast protected nature area in such a way that meets its specific environmental, social and economic needs whilst conserving and enhancing its natural beauty.	Resources form online marketing kit include: Image gallery, Sense of place, Bespoke Itineraries, Room Pack, 'what's on' ideas, Useful links	Collaborative management of the protected marine area
Activities for partners	Networking - 2 meetings per year, on location, inspiring speakers find partners for collaborations. Marketing Campaigns	Jointly produce a protected nature area management plan To review the plan at 5-yearly intervals.	Active Map on website Marketing toolkit to apply to business Examples of businesses using the resource highlighted.	Collaborative projects such as: Wrangle sea bank raising project, Lincolnshire Friskney Sea Lane and saltmarsh access, Lincolnshire Common ground, Boston barrier, Non-Native Marine Species Initiative
Benefits to nature and/or culture	Promote sustainable tourism	According to Action Plan 2014-19: The following themes were managed: Landscape, Biodiversity and Geodiversity; Built and Historic Environment; Farming, Forestry and Fishing Sustainable Communities Access and Recreation	Enhance the value of nature for business by providing information, and tools.	Collaborative nature management
Monitoring and evaluation	Membership needs to be renewed. Not clear how sustainability is monitored.	Strategies are reviewed every 5 years	By relevant organisation	By relevant organisation

5. Programme Geiranger Fjord

The Geiranger fjord has a partnership programme under the Green fjord partnership. The partnership uses its own brand “A pure masterpiece”.

Table 10: Overview of a partnership programme in the Geiranger fjord area

Organization name	Green fjord partnership “Eit reint meisterverk” (‘A pure masterpiece’) brand
Type	Partnership for SMEs in the Geirangerfjord area
Focus	Sustainable tourism
Criteria	Partners need to sign a declaration. Satisfy environmental certification standards where found, such as e.g. Swan label, Environmental lighthouse, ISO 14001, and Innovation Norway's brand for sustainable destinations. In cases where no branding schemes exist, the Steering Group for the Green Fjord decides 2020 in consultation with the relevant professional environment, the use of the brand "Eit reint masterpiece".
Membership/partners	Businesses operating in the protected nature area
Number of partners	-
Funding	-
Benefits to partners	Access to funds and a network of expertise Profiling the business through the brand « Eit pure Masterpiece », according to the given criterion. Possibility to succeed through collaboration with others in a committed partnership
Activities for partners	To work to achieve overall goals in Reputation and the brand strategy for Green Fjord 2020 To show willingness and ability to collaborate To participate with activities such as expertise, experience and entrepreneurship by
Benefits to nature	Sharing experience and taking annual measures; "Rise toward trackless traffic" in the protected area The Green fjord Conference (every second year, February 2020) and partnership meetings when no conference
Monitoring and evaluation	If a partner is deficient in compliance with standards or other approval, one withdraws from the partnerships.

Learnings

Summary of partnership structures

In the previous section an overview of partnership programmes in the scope of this inventory have been illustrated. The common features are:

1. They are voluntary and self-regulating.
2. The partnerships are action oriented and have clear, albeit varied goals.
3. There is limited emphasis on the World Heritage Brand

The partnership programmes described in this inventory focus on collaborative networking using local partners. A transnational partnership, may draw from the local strengths and focus on co-operative networking with activities geared towards sharing knowledge and best practice.

A framework depicting this model of partnerships is given in figure 3.

There is potential to use the World Heritage brand as a stronger link between the protected areas. This needs to be explored further.

Figure 3: Structure of partnership programmes related to Sustainable Tourism (Adapted from Erkuş-Öztürk & Eraydın, 2010).

Proposed success factors for successful transnational protected area collaboration

In order to build a transnational partnership, the process is similar to the tourism partnership process model illustrated by figure 2. However, there is an added complexity of transnationality, multiple stakeholders and varied goals. There are particular conditions that determine the success of such a collaboration. According to varied research, the conditions for success are:

Table 11: Summary of success factors for multi-stakeholder partnerships

(Source: Pattberg & Widerberg, 2016)

Conditions for success	Literature
ACTORS	
Optimal partner mix	Beisheim (2012), Newell et al. (2012)
Effective leadership	Glasbergen (2010), Abbott & Snidal (2010)
PROCESS	
Stringent goal-setting	Liese & Beisheim (2011), Abbott et al. (2000) Keohane & Victor (2011)
Sustained funding	Martens (2007), and Reinicke et al. (2000)
Professional process management	Liese and Beisheim (2011), Szulecki et al. (2011),
Regular monitoring, reporting and evaluation to support organizational learning	Wigell (2008) and Bäckstrand (2012)
CONTEXT	
Active meta-governance	Biermann et al. (2009), Derkx and Glasbergen (2014)
Favourable political and social context	Stringer et al. (2014), Beisheim & Liese (2014)
Fit to problem -structure	Miles et al. (2001), Abbott (2012), Keohane & Victor (2011)

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Beautiful dune landscape and long beach on the island of Amrum at North Sea,
Schleswig-Holstein, Germany
Photo by: jakobradlgruber